

Appendix 1. Table S1–S3

Table S1. Bio-based fertilizers (BBF) assessed in the study and their processing technologies, product function categories (PFC) and component material categories (CMC) according to the Fertilising Products Regulation (2019/1009), and contents of N and P (g kg ⁻¹ dry weight), and As, Cd, Ni and Pb (mg kg ⁻¹ dry weight.)										
BBF	Raw material	Processing technology	PFC ^a	CMC ^b	N	P	As	Cd	Ni	Pb
BA1	Wheat and maize	Fermentation and distillation	1 A-I	4(6) ^c	62.1	13.6	<0.02	0.12	1.43	0.12
MO14	Animal proteins, vegetable by-products, apatite	Pelletising	1 A-I	6(10) ^c	24.9	67.4	3.5	14.9	14.0	3.0
MB1	Meat and bone meal	Pelletising	1 B-I	10	81.3	63.4	0.03	0.02	0.20	0.15
CGO	Struvite	Struvite precipitation	1 C-I	12	102	228	<0.02	0.01	0.85	0.21
ADC	Sewage sludge ash	Thermochemical process	1 C-I	13	0.5	80.5	5.8	0.27	82.2	13.2
OPU	Chicken manure	Pelletising	1 B-I	10	31.5	19.6	1.45	0.73	10.3	0.93
EPH	Sunflower husk ash	Granulating	1 C-I	13	1.3	19.5	0.70	1.50	25.9	3.1
PLA	Poultry litter ash	Incineration	1 C-I	13	0.1	52.3	2.7	1.2	33.1	9.2
VCA	Vermicompost	Composting	1 A-I	3	12.2	2.7	9.2	0.46	34.3	20.5
MO10	Natural origin (plant, animal)	Pelletising	1 B-I	6(10) ^c	46.1	50.9	0.70	4.20	7.6	1.45
OG1	Meat and bone meal	Pelletising	1 B-I	10	108	34.9	<0.02	0.04	1.76	0.37
PCS	Sewage water	Struvite precipitation	1 C-I	12	104	233	<0.02	<0.01	0.09	<0.03
DCP	Ash (incinerated sewage sludge)	P extraction	1 C-I	12	0.4	222	0.57	0.07	3.4	2.8
MBC	Chicken manure	Energy free carbonisation technology	1 A-I	14	29.4	30.6	0.35	0.90	13.4	0.57
MAP	Mining waste or other sources	CleanMAP technology	1 C-I	12	120	249	0.60	<0.001	0.13	<0.03
STR	Sewage sludge	Struvite (electrolysis cell)	1 C-I	12	86	196	2.6	0.09	124	5.1
PKA	Sewage sludge	Incineration	-	13	0.2	22.8	1.84	0.30	65.6	7.5
VVA	Sewage sludge	Magnetic separation of iron phosphate	1 C-I	12	4.5	135	1.89	0.12	38.3	15.8
VVB	Sewage sludge	Magnetic separation of iron phosphate	1 C-I	12	7.8	122	9.9	0.01	72.3	13.5
NNP	Organic municipal and industrial sludges	Vacuum assisted medium wave infrared technology for drying	1 B-I	SS* based	51.5	25.4	2.1	0.56	18.1	13.7
PRV	Biowaste, sewage sludge and food by-products	Biogas process and hygienised	1 B-I	SS* based	29.3	28.5	7.7	0.94	48.7	19.6
RAN	Biowaste and sewage sludge	Drying and granulating	1 B-I	SS* based	40.2	35.2	18.7	1.21	48.5	23.0
CRA	Sludge from juice-making industry	Hydrothermal conversion	1 A-I	14	63.5	9.1	2.1	0.11	22.7	8.5
PPH	Sewage sludge	Thermochemical process	1 C-I	13	0.5	16.8	0.57	0.59	8.5	0.53
BAG	Sewage sludge	Drying and Pyrolysis	-	SS* based	7.6	52.3	10.3	0.12	72.0	74.9
SSW	Sludge and wastewater	Precipitation	1 C-I	12	87.8	213	0.37	0.03	0.70	<0.03

PRC	Waste- and process water	Crystallisation	1 C-I	12	4.9	38.3	0.68	0.08	7.5	9.0
KBT	Molten slag of sewage sludge	Thermochemical process	1 C-I	13	-	110	1.92	2.8	17.2	17.0
ABP	Food grade cattle and other types of bone grist	Pyrolysis	1 A-I	14	14.4	150	<0.02	<0.001	3.2	0.45
DPS	Pig slurry	Digesting	1 A-I	5	40.9	33.4	0.56	0.52	14.4	1.68
DSP	Pig slurry	Solid fraction of the digested pig slurry	1 A-I	5	27.6	18.5	0.17	0.18	8.1	0.47
PPS	Pig slurry	Pyrolyzed solid fraction of pig slurry	1 A-I	14	31.3	43.6	0.31	0.58	17.9	1.42
CPS	Pig slurry	Separated, composted pig slurry	1 A-I	5	19.3	13.2	0.13	0.15	5.6	0.32
PLP	Biowaste, food industry by-products, peat, wood chips	Composting	1 A-I	3	20.1	3.4	4.2	0.26	17.8	15.3
EPS	Wastewater	Struvite precipitation	1 C-I	12	84.0	203	0.54	0.07	159	3.9
BES	Pig slurry	Precipitation	1 C-I	12	64.1	180	<0.02	<0.001	2.6	0.22
CRB	Sludge from wine-making industry	Hydrothermal conversion	1 A-I	14	46.2	28.3	5.6	0.10	28.3	24.0
BA6	Plant-based residues	Fermentation and distillation	1 A-II	4(6) ^c	61.4	13.6	<0.02	0.13	1.61	0.03
BIO	Meat bone meal, apatite, vinasse, poultry manure	Drying and pelletizing	1 B-I	10	78.5	42.5	0.14	0.05	2.5	2.2
ECO	Blood and feather meal	Pelletizing	1 B-I	10	130	1.0	0.03	0.01	1.40	0.34
FEK	Poultry manure	Drying and extrusion process	1 A-I	10	43.7	14.4	0.93	0.37	8.3	1.91
MO13	Feather meal	Pelletizing	1 A-I	10	153	2.2	0.91	<0.001	0.60	0.13
OG2	Horn meal (pig bristles)	Hydrolysis	1 A-I	10	148	3.2	0.05	0.01	0.68	0.08
PAL	Fermented biochar, clay and rock flour	Pyrolysis and fermentation	1 A-I	4	53.9	9.6	1.88	0.08	7.3	2.1

^a PFC 1 A-I: Solid organic fertilizer: ≥ 15% organic C, PFC 1 A-II: Liquid organic fertilizer: ≥ 5% organic C, PFC 1 B-I: Solid organo-mineral fertilizer: ≥ 7.5% organic C, 1 B-II: Liquid organo-mineral fertilizer: ≥ 3% organic C, 1 C-I: Straight solid inorganic macronutrient fertilizer, and 1 C-II: Compound solid inorganic macronutrient fertilizer (EU 2019/1009).

^b CMC 3: Compost, CMC 4: Fresh crop digestate, CMC 5: Digestate other than fresh crop digestate, CMC 6: Food industry by-products, CMC 10: Derived products within the meaning of Animal By-products Regulation, CMC 12: Precipitated phosphate salts or derivatives, CMC 13: Thermal oxidation materials or derivatives and CMC 14: Pyrolysis or gasification materials (EU 2019/1009).

^c For BBFs which belong to more than one CMC group, the secondary CMC group is included in brackets.

*Sewage sludge

Table S2. Initial values (after the first year of model calculation) for PTEs in soil (mg kg^{-1}) and soil water ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$), and PTE fluxes in leaching and erosion (g ha^{-1}) for the six target countries. Fertilizers and crops had negligible effects on these initial values.

PTE	Country	PTE in soil (mg kg^{-1})	PTE in soil water ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)	Leaching of PTE (g ha^{-1})	PTE in erosion (g ha^{-1})
As	Denmark	4.1	1.7	5.0	3.5
	Finland	3.3	1.3	2.7	1.6
	France	32	15	61	75
	Germany	13	6.1	18	35
	Hungary	8.6	4.0	12	18
	Spain	8.7	12	49	40
Cd	Denmark	0.18	0.16	0.47	0.15
	Finland	0.17	0.14	0.29	0.09
	France	0.29	0.04	0.17	0.66
	Germany	0.28	0.04	0.13	0.75
	Hungary	0.19	0.03	0.09	0.40
	Spain	0.19	0.03	0.11	0.90
Ni	Denmark	5.7	14	41	4.8
	Finland	14	1.9	3.9	7.1
	France	20	1.7	6.9	46
	Germany	27	2.3	6.9	72
	Hungary	26	2.3	6.8	55
	Spain	28	4.0	15.9	129
Pb	Denmark	12	0.45	1.3	9.9
	Finland	10	0.38	0.76	5.0
	France	32	0.12	0.47	73
	Germany	25	0.09	0.27	66
	Hungary	16	0.06	0.18	33
	Spain	21	0.21	0.86	96

Table S3. Initial values (after the first year of model calculation) for PTEs in wheat and maize grains and carrot roots (mg kg⁻¹ DM), and PTE offtake in yield (g ha⁻¹) for the six target countries. Fertilizers had negligible effects on these initial values.

PTE	Country	Wheat		Maize		Carrot	
		PTE content (µg kg ⁻¹ DM)	PTE offtake (g ha ⁻¹)	PTE content (µg kg ⁻¹ DM)	PTE offtake (g ha ⁻¹)	PTE content (µg kg ⁻¹ DM)	PTE offtake (g ha ⁻¹)
As	Denmark	98	0.65	3.8	0.02	32	0.36
	Finland	3.3	0.01			25	0.21
	France	780	4.7	60	0.45	250	2.2
	Germany	310	2.1	33	0.27	100	1.2
	Hungary	42	0.19	22	0.13	67	0.59
	Spain	1500	4.5	16	0.16	68	0.48
Cd	Denmark	8.0	0.05	0.93	0.01	19	0.22
	Finland	22	0.07			66	0.55
	France	37	0.23	32	0.24	23	0.20
	Germany	36	0.24	37	0.30	22	0.26
	Hungary	23	0.10	38	0.23	15	0.13
	Spain	5.9	0.02	21	0.22	16	0.11
Ni	Denmark	100	0.67	34	0.20	460	5.3
	Finland	110	0.36			290	2.5
	France	350	2.2	290	2.2	1600	14
	Germany	480	3.2	120	0.98	2200	25
	Hungary	370	1.6	120	0.72	2100	19
	Spain	1500	4.4	410	4.2	2300	16
Pb	Denmark	2.0	0.01	14	0.08	170	2.0
	Finland	100	0.32			52	0.43
	France	5.4	0.03	0.06	0.00	460	4.1
	Germany	4.2	0.03	2.1	0.02	360	4.1
	Hungary	3.8	0.02	480	2.9	230	2.1
	Spain	12	0.03	0.04	0.00	300	2.1

Appendix 2. Model parameters for mass balance calculations of arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni) and lead (Pb) for Finland, Denmark, Germany, France, Spain, and Hungary

Common parameters used for Finland

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Annual runoff	mm	200	Finnish Environment Institute 2000
Annual erosion	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	500	Finnish Environment Institute 2000
Average liming rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	400	Farmit 2010
Average P fertilization rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		10	FAOLEX:Finland 2023; P fertilizer rates for soils in satisfactory P level
Barley		10	
Oats		10	"
Rye		10	"
Potato		55	"
Carrot		40	"
Sunflower		-	Not grown in Finland
Maize		-	Not grown in Finland
Average DM yield level	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		3 225	Eurostat 2013–2022
Barley		3 150	Eurostat 2013–2022
Oats		2 973	Eurostat 2013–2022
Rye		2 960	Eurostat 2013–2022
Potato, 26 000 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 22%		5 720	Eurostat 2013–2022
Carrot, 41860 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 20%		8 372	Eurostat 2013–2022
Sunflower		-	
Maize		-	

Finland As

Model parameter (As)	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	3.3	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007b, Table 1, Salo et al. 2018a, Reimann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.96	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 40
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	2 421	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Finnish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	2.8	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 17
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		0.7	Salo et al. 2018b
BBF high in metals		5.75	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.001	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007a, calculated from tables 39 and 58
Barley		0.015	Salo et al. 2018a
Oats		0.008	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.008	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.005	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.008	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		-	-
Maize		-	-

Finland Cd

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.17	Mean of Mäkelä-Kurtto et al.2003, Salo et al. 2018a, Reinmann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.35	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 40
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	1 213	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Finnish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.15	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 17
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ P		
Mineral phosphate		2.5	Salo et al. 2018b
BBF high in metals		77.4	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.06	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.130	Smolders 2013
Barley		0.036	Salo et al. 2018a
Oats		0.083	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.083	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.118	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.379	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		-	-
Maize		-	-

Finland Ni

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	14.1	Mean of Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2003, Salo et al. 2018a, Reimann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	1.63	Kyllönen et al. 2012
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	7 332	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Finnish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	8.3	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 17
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		1.00	Salo et al. 2018b
BBF high in metals		82.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.85	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.008	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007a, Table 60
Barley		0.003	Salo et al. 2018a
Oats		0.050	Mean of wheat and barley multiplied by 10 to reach observed grain concentrations (Soinne et al. 2022)
Rye		0.005	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.010	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.021	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		-	
Maize		-	

Finland Pb

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	10.0	Mean of Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2003, Salo et al. 2018a, Reimann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	8.6	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 40
Soil adsorption coefficient (K_d)	l kg ⁻¹	26 145	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Finnish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	1.5	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007c, Table 17
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		0.19	Salo et al. 2018b
BBF high in metals		13.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.21	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.001	Mäkelä-Kurtto et al. 2007a, Table 60
Barley		0.001	Salo et al. 2018a
Oats		0.006	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.006	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.001	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.005	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		-	
Maize		-	

Common parameters used for Denmark

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Annual runoff	mm	299	Petersen et al. 2021
Annual erosion	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	850	Onnen et al. 2019
Average liming rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	240	Use in statistics 593000 t a ⁻¹ in 2021 for 2.5 million ha
Average P fertilization rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		19	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Barley		21	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Oats		23	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Rye		18	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Potato		30	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Carrot		30	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Sunflower		-	Not among recommendations
Maize		30	Landbrugsstyrelsen 2022
Average DM yield level	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		6 656	Eurostat 2013–2022
Barley		4 894	Eurostat 2013–2022
Oats		4 361	Eurostat 2013–2022
Rye		5 130	Eurostat 2013–2022
Potato, 42000 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 22%		9 245	Eurostat 2013–2022
Carrot, 57500 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 20%		11 499	Eurostat 2013–2022
Sunflower		2 275	Eurostat 2013–2022
Maize		5 767	Eurostat 2013–2022

Denmark As

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	4.1	Reinmann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	1.8	Bak et al. 1997
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	2 421	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Finnish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	20	50% of EU fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		5.3	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		5.75	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.024	Lex4Bio field experiment median
Barley		0.013	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.005	Salo et al. 2018
Carrot		0.008	Salo et al. 2018
Sunflower		-	
Maize		0.001	Lex4Bio field experiment median

Denmark Cd

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.18	Reinmann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.2	Ellerman et al. 2023
Soil adsorption coefficient (K_d)	l kg ⁻¹	1 134	Holm et al. 2003
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	1.0	www2.skovognatur.dk
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ P		
Mineral phosphate		61.3	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		77.4	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.06	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.045	Lex4Bio field experiment, median
Barley		0.176	Lex4Bio field experiment, in Denmark
Oats		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.135	Smolders 2001 (Sweden and the Netherlands)
Carrot		0.110	Smolders 2001 (Sweden)
Sunflower		-	
Maize		0.005	Lex4Bio field experiment

Denmark Ni

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	5.7	Reinmann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	3.2	Bak et al. 1997
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	418	Vandenhove et al. 2009b (mean of clay, sand and organic soil)
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	6.0	www2.skovognatur.dk
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		29	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		82.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.85	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.018	Lex4Bio field experiment, median
Barley		0.020	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Rye		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Potato		0.020	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, tubers
Carrot		0.081	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, root crops
Sunflower		-	
Maize		0.006	Lex4Bio field experiment, median

Denmark Pb

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	11.7	Reinmann et al. 2014
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	5.0	Ellerman et al. 2023
Soil adsorption coefficient (K_d)	l kg ⁻¹	26 145	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Finnish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	5.0	www2.skovognatur.dk
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		4.2	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		13.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.21	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.0002	Lex4Bio, field experiments, median
Barley		0.0011	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Rye		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Potato		0.0015	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, tubers
Carrot		0.0146	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, root crops
Sunflower		-	
Maize		0.0012	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, maize grains

Common parameters used for Germany

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Annual runoff	mm	299	Same as in Denmark
Annual erosion	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	2 700	Auerswald et al. 2009
Average liming rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	123	National statistics in 2007
Average P fertilization rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		27	Düngeverordnung 2017
Barley		25	Düngeverordnung 2017
Oats		16	Düngeverordnung 2017
Rye		19	Düngeverordnung 2017
Potato		24	Düngeverordnung 2017
Carrot		20	Düngeverordnung 2017
Sunflower		14	Düngeverordnung 2017
Maize		8	Düngeverordnung 2017
Average DM yield level	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		6 651	Eurostat 2013–2022
Barley		6 154	Eurostat 2013–2022
Oats		3 898	Eurostat 2013–2022
Rye		5 130	Eurostat 2013–2022
Potato, 42000 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 22%		9 267	Eurostat 2013–2022
Carrot, 57500 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 20%		11 499	Eurostat 2013–2022
Sunflower		1 916	Eurostat 2013–2022
Maize		8 087	Eurostat 2013–2022

Germany As

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	13.0	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	1.8	Same as in Denmark
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	2.139	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	6.2	Dittrich and Klose 2008
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		3.6	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		5.75	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.024	Lex4Bio field experiments, median
Barley		0.013	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.005	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.008	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		0.048	Piracha et al. 2022
Maize		0.003	Lex4Bio field experiment in Germany

Germany Cd

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.3	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.25	Six and Smolders 2014
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	6 659	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.5	Dittrich and Klose 2008
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ P		
Mineral phosphate		12.3	Verbeek et al. (2020)
BBF high in metals		77.4	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.06	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.130	Smolders 2001, Six and Smolders 2014
Barley		0.176	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Rye		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Potato		0.070	Smolders 2001, Six and Smolders 2014
Carrot		0.080	Smolders 2001
Sunflower		1.250	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Maize		0.133	Lex4Bio field experiment in Germany

Germany Ni

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	26.7	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	3.2	Same as in Denmark
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	11 519	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	3.6	Dittrich and Klose 2008
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		10	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		82.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.85	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.018	Lex4Bio field experiments median
Barley		0.020	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Rye		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Potato		0.020	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, tubers
Carrot		0.081	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, root crops
Sunflower		0.030	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.005	Lex4Bio field experiment in Germany

Germany Pb

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	24.5	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.6	Nickel et al. 2015
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	269 163	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	38	Dittrich and Klose 2008
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		2.1	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		13.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.21	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.0002	Lex4Bio, field experiments, median
Barley		0.0011	Lex4Bio, field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Rye		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Potato		0.0015	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, tubers
Carrot		0.0146	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, root crops
Sunflower		0.0047	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.0001	Lex4Bio, field experiment in Germany

Common parameters used for France

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Annual runoff	mm	400	Dupas et al. 2015
Annual erosion	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	2 300	Eurostat, RUSLE 2016
Average liming rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	54	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Average P fertilization rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹ dry mass		
Wheat		21	Recommendations based on yield levels and P demand from Comifer 2019
Barley		15	
Oats		12	
Rye		10	
Potato		17	
Carrot		18	
Sunflower		10	
Maize		18	
Average DM yield level	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		6 089	Eurostat 2013–2022
Barley		5 527	Eurostat 2013–2022
Oats		3 771	Eurostat 2013–2022
Rye		3 699	Eurostat 2013–2022
Potato, 41800 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 22%		9 206	Eurostat 2013–2022
Carrot, 44000 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 20%		8 813	Eurostat 2013–2022
Sunflower		2 063	Eurostat 2013–2022
Maize		7 466	Eurostat 2013–2022

France As

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	32.5	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	12	Data and statistical studies 2021
Soil adsorption coefficient (K_d)	l kg ⁻¹	2 139	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	2.7	AFNOR 2017
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		7.1	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		5.75	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.024	Lex4Bio field experiments, median
Barley		0.013	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley
Rye		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley
Potato		0.005	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.008	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		0.048	Piracha et al. 2022
Maize		0.002	Lex4Bio field experiment in France

France Cd

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.3	Mean of Reimann 2014, Sterckeman et al. 2018 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.25	Sterckeman et al. 2018, Six and Smolders 2014
Soil adsorption coefficient (K_d)	l kg ⁻¹	6 659	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.35	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ P		
Mineral phosphate		73.5	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		77.4	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.06	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.130	Sterckeman et al. 2018, Smolders 2001, Six and Smolders 2014
Barley		0.240	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Oats		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Rye		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Potato		0.083	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Carrot		0.080	Smolders 2001
Sunflower		1.250	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Maize		0.110	Sterckeman et al. 2018

France Ni

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	19.9	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	15	Scientific Interest Group on Soils 2011a
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	11 519	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	35	AFNOR 2017
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		18	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		82.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.85	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.018	Lex4Bio field experiments, median
Barley		0.020	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Rye		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Potato		0.020	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, tubers
Carrot		0.081	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, root crops
Sunflower		0.030	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.015	Lex4Bio, field experiments in France

France Pb

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	31.8	Mean of Reimann 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	30	Scientific Interest Group on Soils 2011b
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	269 163	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	3.1	AFNOR 2017
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		3.8	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		13.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.21	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.0002	Lex4Bio field experiments, median
Barley		0.0011	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Rye		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Potato		0.0015	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, tubers
Carrot		0.0146	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, root crops
Sunflower		0.0047	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.0002 ×10 ⁻²	Lex4Bio field experiment in France

Common parameters used for Spain

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Annual runoff	mm	400	Same as in France
Annual erosion	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	4 600	Eurostat, 2016 RUSLE estimation
Average liming rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	54	Same as in France
Average P fertilization rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		21	Same as in France
Barley		15	Same as in France
Oats		12	Same as in France
Rye		10	Same as in France
Potato		17	Same as in France
Carrot		18	Same as in France
Sunflower		10	Same as in France
Maize		18	Same as in France
Average DM yield level	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		2 989	Eurostat 2013–2022
Barley		2 914	Eurostat 2013–2022
Oats		1 800	Eurostat 2013–2022
Rye		1 969	Eurostat 2013–2022
Potato, 31600 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 22%		6 963	Eurostat 2013–2022
Carrot, 58310 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 12%		6 997	Eurostat 2013–2022
Sunflower		1 058	Eurostat 2013–2022
Maize		10 021	Eurostat 2013–2022

Spain As

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	8.8	Mean of Reimann et al. 2014 and Lex4Bio soils
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	12	Same as in France
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	713	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Spanish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	40	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		6.1	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		5.75	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.171	Lex4Bio field experiment in Spain
Barley		0.013	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Rye		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Potato		0.005	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.008	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		0.048	Piracha et al. 2022
Maize		0.002	Lex4Bio, field experiment in France

Spain Cd

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.2	Mean of Reinman 2014 and Lex4Bio studies
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.3	Six and Smolders 2014
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	7 400	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Spanish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	2.0	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ P		
Mineral phosphate		122.5	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		77.4	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.06	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.030	Lex4Bio field experiment in Spain
Barley		0.240	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Oats		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Rye		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley in Denmark
Potato		0.083	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Carrot		0.080	Smolders 2001
Sunflower		1.250	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Maize		0.110	Sterckeman et al. 2018

Spain Ni

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	28.0	Mean of Reimann et al. 2014 and Lex4Bio soils
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	15.0	Same as in France
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	7 044	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Spanish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	90	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		22	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		82.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.85	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.052	Lex4Bio field experiment in Spain
Barley		0.020	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Rye		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Potato		0.020	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, tubers
Carrot		0.081	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, root crops
Sunflower		0.030	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.015	Lex4Bio field experiment in France

Spain Pb

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	20.9	Mean of Reimann et al. 2014 and Lex4Bio soils
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	30.0	Same as in France
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	97614	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, Spanish clay soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	120	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		9.7	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		13.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.21	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.0006	Lex4Bio field experiment in Spain
Barley		0.0011	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Rye		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Potato		0.0015	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, tubers
Carrot		0.0146	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, root crops
Sunflower		0.0047	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.0002 × 10 ⁻²	Lex4Bio field experiment in France

Common parameters used for Hungary

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Annual runoff	mm	299	Same as in Denmark and Germany
Annual erosion	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	2 100	Eurostat, RUSLE 2016
Average liming rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	123	Same as in Germany
Average P fertilization rate	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		27	Same as in Germany
Barley		25	Same as in Germany
Oats		16	Same as in Germany
Rye		19	Same as in Germany
Potato		24	Same as in Germany
Carrot		20	Same as in Germany
Sunflower		14	Same as in Germany
Maize		8	Same as in Germany
Average DM yield level	kg ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹		
Wheat		4 460	Eurostat 2013–2022
Barley		4 540	Eurostat 2013–2022
Oats		2 393	Eurostat 2013–2022
Rye		2 712	Eurostat 2013–2022
Potato, 25200 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 22%		5 541	Eurostat 2013–2022
Carrot, 43900 FM kg ha ⁻¹ , DM 20%		8 783	Eurostat 2013–2022
Sunflower		2 449	Eurostat 2013–2022
Maize		6 054	Eurostat 2013–2022

Hungary As

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	8.7	Mean of Reinmann et al. (2014) and Lex4Bio experiments
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	12	Same as in France
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	2 139	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	40	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		2.30	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		5.75	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.005	Lex4Bio field experiment in Hungary
Barley		0.013	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley used for Denmark
Rye		0.018	Mean of wheat and barley used for Denmark
Potato		0.005	Salo et al. 2018a
Carrot		0.008	Salo et al. 2018a
Sunflower		0.048	Piracha et al. 2022
Maize		0.003	Lex4Bio field experiment in Germany

Hungary Cd

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	0.2	Mean of Reinmann et al. 2014 and Lex4Bio experiments
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	0.4	Six and Smolders 2014
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	6 659	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	2.0	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ P		
Mineral phosphate		61.3	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		77.4	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.06	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.117	Lex4Bio field experiment in Hungary
Barley		0.176	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley used for Denmark
Rye		0.111	Mean of wheat and barley used for Denmark
Potato		1.000	Mirecki et al. 2015
Carrot		0.080	Smolders 2001
Sunflower		1.250	Sterckeman et al. 2018
Maize		0.200	Mirecki et al. 2015

Hungary Ni

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	26.1	Mean of Reinmann et al. 2014 and Lex4Bio experiments
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	15	Same as in France
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	11 519	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	90	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		12.0	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		82.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.85	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.014	Lex4Bio field experiment in Hungary
Barley		0.020	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Rye		0.041	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, cereals
Potato		0.020	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, tubers
Carrot		0.081	Vandenhove et al. 2009a, root crops
Sunflower		0.030	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.005	Lex4Bio field experiment in Germany

Hungary Pb

Model parameter	Unit	Value	Reference / remarks
Total concentration in soil	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	15.9	Mean of Reinmann et al. 2014 and Lex4Bio experiments
Aerial deposition	g ha ⁻¹ y ⁻¹	30	Same as in France
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _d)	l kg ⁻¹	269 163	Lex4Bio, rainfall simulator study, German loam soil, Ylivainio et al. 2023
Concentration in liming materials	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass	120	EU Fertiliser law 2023
Concentration in fertilizer	mg kg ⁻¹ dry mass		
Mineral phosphate		2.3	Verbeeck et al. 2020
BBF high in metals		13.2	Lex4Bio, field experiments
BBF low in metals		0.21	Lex4Bio, field experiments
Soil-to-plant transfer factor	-		
Wheat		0.0002	Lex4Bio field experiment in Hungary
Barley		0.0011	Lex4Bio field experiment in Denmark
Oats		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Rye		0.0107	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, cereals
Potato		0.0450	Mirecki et al. 2015
Carrot		0.0146	Vandenhove et al. 2009b, root crops
Sunflower		0.0047	IAEA 1994, grain samples
Maize		0.0300	Mirecki et al. 2015

Appendix 3. SAS code used in the mass balance modelling

This example shows the calculation of cadmium flows for wheat in 0–20 cm soil top layer for the simulation period of 100 years. Bolded variables after first simulation year are shown in tables of results and Appendix 4.

do i = 1 to 100;

**Element inputs calculated based on application rates and contents;*

InMineralFertilizerCd_gha=P_rate_kghawheat*Cd_conc_inMF_per_P_mgkg/**1000**;

InLimingMaterialCd_gha=Lime_rate_kgha*Lime_Cd_mgkg/**1000**;

InFertilizerProductCd_gha=BBF_application_rate*BBF_element_concentration/**1000**;

Added_in_Fertilizers=InMineralFertilizerCd_gha+InFertilizerProductCd_gha;

**Soil element contents after annual fertilizer application;*

Soil_mgCd_kgSoil = Soil_mgCd_kgSoil + **1000***Added_in_Fertilizers/(**2*****1000*****1000*****1**);

PlantUptake_gha = Soil_mgCd_kgSoil*(Yield_DM_kghawheat)/**1000***TF_Cdwheat;

PlantContent_gkg=PlantUptake_gha/(Yield_DM_kghawheat);

SoilWater_Cd_mgl=Soil_mgCd_kgSoil/Kd_lkg_Cd;

Leaching_Cd_gha=Annual_runoff_litre*SoilWater_Cd_mgl/**1000**;

SoilErosion_Cd_gha=Annual_erosion_kgha*Soil_mgCd_kgSoil/**1000**;

**Annual flows of element;*

Annual_Input=InMineralFertilizerCd_gha+InLimingMaterialCd_gha+

InFertilizerProductCd_gha+Deposition_Cd_g_ha_year;

Annual_Output=PlantUptake_gha+Leaching_Cd_gha+SoilErosion_Cd_gha;

Annual_Balance_= Annual_Input-Annual_Output;

AnnualBalance_in_Soil = InLimingMaterialCd_gha + Deposition__Cd_g_ha_year - PlantUptake_gha-Leaching_Cd_gha-SoilErosion_Cd_gha;

**Soil content after annual element flows;*

Soil_mgCd_kgSoil = Soil_mgCd_kgSoil +**1000***AnnualBalance_in_Soil/(**2*****1000*****1000*****1**);

**Accumulated flows during the simulation;*

Sum_of_fertilizers=Sum_of_fertilizers + InMineralFertilizerCd_gha ;

SumOfLimingMaterials= SumOfLimingMaterials + InLimingMaterialCd_gha;

SumOfFertilizerProducts= SumOfFertilizerProducts +InFertilizerProductCd_gha;

Sum_of_Deposition=Sum_of_Deposition + Deposition__Cd_g_ha_year;

Sum_of_Leaching = Sum_of_Leaching+ Leaching_Cd_gha;

Sum_of_SoilErosion = Sum_of_SoilErosion + SoilErosion_Cd_gha;

Sum_of_PlantUptake =Sum_of_PlantUptake+PlantUptake_gha;

Sum_of_Losses_to_Environment=Sum_of_Losses_to_Environment+ Leaching_Cd_gha +SoilErosion_Cd_gha;

Accumulated_input =Accumulated_input+input;

Accumulated_output = Accumulated_output +output;

Explanation for the calculation of soil mass in top 20 cm layer:

The equation $2 \times 1000 \times 1000 \times 1$ shows the soil mass in which PTE applications are mixed, and there 2 represents 20 cm soil depth as dm, 1000×1000 represents area of hectare in dm^2 and 1 represents dry soil bulk density as kg dm^{-3} .

References in Appendix

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